

The United States Navy Electronic Chart Display
and Information (ECDIS) Development Project

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ABSTRACT

The United States Navy has an Electronic Chart Display & Information System (ECDIS) currently in full scale development. This system is called the Navigation Sensor System Interface, or NAVSSI (AN/SSN-6). The NAVSSI will utilize the Digital Nautical Chart (DNC) database for navigation. The DNC is a global marine charting database being developed by the United States Defense Mapping Agency (DMA). Use of the DNC with NAVSSI will replace the use of paper charts for safe ownship navigation. Our goal is for Navy ships to be relying on NAVSSI with DNC and not paper navigation charts by the year 2000.

This paper will present a background on the NAVSSI project and description of the system hardware and software. NAVSSI compliance with ECDIS performance standards will be discussed as well as some unique Navy missions satisfied by the NAVSSI. The NAVSSI accepts inputs from the Global Positioning System (GPS), OMEGA, TRANSIT (SATNAV) and inertial navigation systems (ex. AN/WSN-5) and these inputs are filtered to provide the best available position, attitude and time data. This data is distributed to combat and weapon systems via networks or point-to-point interfaces. The design of the Digital Nautical Chart (DNC) database and the software that has been developed to display and operate the DNC will be covered in depth. The database design required new digital standards which were developed by the Navy and DMA.

BACKGROUND

The concepts of a central navigation data distribution computer and an electronic chart machine have their origins in fleet exercises during the late 1970's and early 1980's. Growing use of satellite navigation data and the increase in weapon system ranges required individual ships within the battlegroup to work with a common navigation picture. Due to the large variety

of navigation data sources found among the battlegroup elements and the lack of a system for integration, operators found it difficult to correlate battlegroup navigation data. The need was recognized for a central navigation data distribution computer and a Tentative Operational Requirement (TOR) for the "Navigation Similar Source Integrator(NAVSSI)" was created (CNO, 1986). In addition, the need for an electronic chart machine was recognized and a TOR was created for the "Universal Tactical Plotter(UTP)" (CNO, 1987).

Various development and procurement options were examined from industry and laboratory sources. Due to multiple existing development efforts and the desire to incorporate an electronic chart database, the proposal to design the system using internal Navy engineering resources was accepted. The formal Operational Requirement (OR) for the "Navigation Sensor System Interface" was approved by the Chief of Naval Operations in June 1991 (CNO, 1991). The NAVSSI program formally commenced in February 1991. The NAVSSI program is managed by the Space and Naval Warfare Systems Command (SPAWAR) PMW 167, Navigation Systems Division.

SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

The NAVSSI can be divided into three pieces; the Display & Control Subsystem (DCS), Real Time Subsystem (RTS) and the Navigators Workstation (NWS).

The DCS uses the Navy Tactical Applications Computer III (TAC III). The TAC III is based on Hewlett Packard workstations operating with HP-UNIX. The DCS will be responsible for performing the man-machine interface functions and all DNC chart display/operation functions. The DCS is the ECDIS portion of the NAVSSI. The DCS software has been developed in the "C" programming language. The software is being integrated into the Unified Build (UB) environment to allow for a common man-machine interface and to facilitate integration into several shipboard networks.

The Real Time Subsystem (RTS) consists primarily of a VME expansion cabinet connected to the DCS via fiber optic ethernet. The processor board is Motorola based (68040) with a real-time Ada kernel (PSOS+). The RTS will handle all input and output required for navigation data integration and distribution. The Ada software for the RTS is multi-tasking. The software is primarily interrupt driven with some periodic tasks to maintain a current database of navigation parameters.

The NWS is a terminal located on the bridge of the ship. The capabilities of the NWS will vary dependent upon the mission of the ship. At a minimum, the NWS will serve as the bridge display of the ECDIS. The NWS will allow full operation of the DNC database and full access to the NAVSSI system. The DCS is primarily the route planning terminal for NAVSSI and the NWS is primarily the navigation station (route monitoring).

The DNC display becomes the focal point of operator interface with the system. It will provide for the graphical display of ownship navigation and tactical plotting. The need to maintain an ownship position plot is basic to the mariner (Bowditch, 1977). To ensure safety in navigation, the need for and use of accurate navigational products is mandated in United States law (10 U.S.C. 2791-94, 44 U.S.C. 1336). The current methods of manual plotting involving paper charts are labor intensive.

Essential to the mission of the ship is the availability of a survivable navigation system (CNO, 1988). The consistent availability of satellite information for a ownship position fix is questionable in times of hostility. A survivable navigation system should allow the vessel to continue its mission with a high degree of confidence in the reported ownship position. NAVSSI will provide for graceful degradation in the event of failure of one or more sensors (ex. unavailability of GPS). The NAVSSI will serve as the survivable navigation system.

The NAVSSI system is currently being integrated into the Joint Maritime Command and Information System (JMCIS). JMCIS is a C⁴I system being designed and managed by SPAWAR PD60. JMCIS will further couple most of the information and combat systems in surface ships in a network environment.

DIGITAL NAUTICAL CHART (DNC) DATABASE/SOFTWARE

The idea of the electronic chart is not new, as the Navy has realized for some time that these questions must one day be addressed (Clawson, Langran 1986). As a result of an investigation into existing DMA products and commercial products, a determination was made that a new digital database from DMA would be required. A technical specification was developed by the Navy in April 1989 which introduced the concept of a layered database for the digital nautical chart. The technical specification was accepted and validated by DMA in October 1989.

Description

The DNC is a general purpose global database designed to support marine navigation and geographic information systems (GIS). The database is a vector based product that portrays selected significant maritime physical features in a format suitable for computerized marine navigation (MIL-D-89023, Nov 93).

Highlights from the DNC product specification are listed below:

Database sources - DNC is composed of Harbor, Approach, Coastal and General paper charts. Can be created from DX-90 source data.

Horizontal Accuracy - 90% circular error at WGS 84.

Vertical Accuracy - 90% linear error at the vertical datum.

Horizontal Datum - WGS 84.

Vertical Datum - Three datums:

Topographic features - Mean Sea Level
Shoreline - Mean High Water
Hydrographic features - Low Water Tide Level

Unit of Measure - Metric.

Structure - Relationally structured.

Content - Thematically layered; Cultural landmarks, Earth cover, Environment, Hydrography, Inland Waterways, Land Cover, Limits, Aids to Navigation, Obstructions, Port facilities, Relief and Data quality.

Media - Compact Disc - Read Only Memory (CD-ROM).

Tile Size - Seamless database implemented using the World Geographic Reference System(GEOREF).

Format - Vector Product Format(VPF)(MIL-STD-600006).

Prototyping History

The initial DNC prototype was developed as part of the Digital Chart of the World (DCW) effort. The prototype dataset was released in October 1991. The structure was an early version of the Vector Product Format (VPF). Coverage was very minimal, consisting of two NOAA charts of Hampton Roads and two British Admiralty charts for Southern England.

The second DNC prototype was released in July 1992. There were numerous revisions to both the VPF and the DNC product specification. The coverage was just a repeat of the NOAA charts from prototype 1. This version was used by the Navy for significant hardware testing. Work with prototype 2 helped define the graphical requirements for the NAVSSI system.

The third prototype of DNC was released in January 1993. This prototype included additional coverage beyond Hampton Roads to the New York area. This additional coverage was scheduled for use by the Coast Guard and the ECDIS Testbed Project.

The fourth prototype was released in June 1993. This prototype included additional enhancements to the VPF and the product specification. Final incremental changes were made to the VPF and prototype 4A was released in Dec 1993. This is the version of DNC that the NAVSSI is currently operating with. The VPF and DNC product specifications are now finalized.

The coverage of prototype 4A is identified below:

<u>Chart</u>	<u>Scale</u>	<u>Edition</u>	<u>Date</u>
12200	1:419,706	40	9 May 92
12207	1:80,000	18	20 Jun 92
12210	1:80,000	32	10 Oct 92
12211	1:80,000	35	29 Aug 92
12221	1:80,000	60	29 Feb 92
12222	1:40,000	34	23 May 92
12245	1:20,000	51	19 Sep 92
12254	1:20,000	35	28 Mar 92
13003	1:1,200,000	39	25 May 91

Prototype 5 has recently been released (Jan 94). This provides coverage in the Bangor, WA area. DMA is currently finalizing digital production plans for DNC. DMA anticipates providing worldwide coverage for DNC by 1998. It is estimated that approximately 30 CD-ROM's will be needed for worldwide DNC coverage.

Legal Concerns

There is concern regarding the maritime laws and use of the electronic chart. It appears that drastic changes in the existing maritime laws will not be required to accommodate electronic chart display systems. The chartmakers (and the database producers) liability resides on two issues, negligence and/or defective products.

"Whether the chartmaker is to be found liable in any given situation is dependent upon two legal theories: (1) negligence, i.e. where there are definite errors in navigational aids; or (2) products liability, i.e., where the product may accurately portray information but its design was defective. The former is the one most readers are familiar with. The latter is a rather new concept, not yet applied to the nautical chart producer but developing in the aeronautical chart arena. There are significant differences between these two legal theories, very important to the government and the private sector, but for different compelling reasons. The United States Government has not consented to be sued for defective products and may only be sued for negligence. The private chartmaker on the other hand faces lawsuits grounded on both theories." (Obloy, 1989)

Exactly how this liability will apply to electronic chart display systems, operators and database producers is yet

to be resolved. Certain minimum standards for shipboard navigation with NAVSSI will be established and promulgated, as exists with the paper nautical chart. Until the NAVSSI system matures and some fleet feedback regarding electronic chart operation is received, many of these questions will remain unanswered.

There are numerous commercial systems on the market that serve as aids to navigation. The manufacturers accept no liability regarding the navigators use of their systems during navigation. The laws regarding the use of paper charts still apply. Almost all commercial systems scan the available nautical charts and present a raster image on the screen. There are a range of systems available including pure software solutions up through customized hardware and software. In all cases these systems serve only as aids to navigation (in a similar manner to position sources or speed/heading devices). In the future, when the international standards are finalized and legal databases are available to the manufacturers, systems may emerge which can be used for legal ownship plotting while navigating. The systems should comply with all of the ECDIS performance standards. It is unknown to what extent (if any) the manufacturer would accept liability. One of the conditions of purchase may well be a limited or whole liability release for the manufacturer.

Updating

The DMA and Navy are studying several ideas for updating the DNC database. The minimum update method would consist of the operator receiving a NTM or chart update via traditional means, then entering the correction into an overlay in the computer system memory. The overlay would be displayed automatically when the feature or area corrected was displayed. Remember the underlying DNC database can not be altered by the operator due to the read only media. This is analogous to the existing situation with the paper chart.

Several automated methods of updating are under study. The intent is to develop a method which minimizes impact to the operator but provides maximum integrity in the DNC updating. The navigator should be able to confirm and produce reports confirming what updates have occurred.

Two methods have emerged which hold the greatest promise. A design is underway to establish procedures and link the systems necessary to transmit updates via existing communications channels. The NAVSSI would automatically accept and process the updates and provide a report to the operator.

The second method would involve splitting the DNC into two CD-ROM's, one containing the "static" portion of the database and the other containing the "dynamic" portion. This method is under study as an alternative.

Operating NAVSSI with the DNC

This section describes the current scheme for operating NAVSSI with the DNC database. The default navigation display will be presented on the monitor of the DCS and the NWS upon power up (source data dependent upon ownship position) and the ownship symbol will respond to movement as input by the navigation sensors or simulators.

The display can be operated in two modes, relative or geographic. In the relative mode, the ownship stays "fixed" in the center and displayed data moves "relative" to ownship. In geographic mode, the display remains static and the ownship position and other dynamic elements move on the screen. It is believed that the geographic mode will be the most useful and best understood. This also requires less database access and screen rewrites. There will be a "window" surrounding the ownship position which will be stored in memory within the computer system. As the ownship position moves to within some predefined boundary near the window edge, the display will be rewritten, placing the ownship either near the middle of the display or heading away from the edge of the display towards the center. This will be optimized to be virtually transparent to the operator. The goal (which has been accomplished) was to prevent the operator from waiting for the system to both query the database and then write to the screen. The database access will be carried out in the background. The software will keep the window "filled", subject to constraints imposed by operator choice.

The software of the DCS provides full software functionality as required by ECDIS. The operator can zoom, pan and manipulate the display within constraints regarding the safety of navigation. Tools are provided to assist the navigator in calculations for route planning

(ex. waypoints) and monitoring. Pop up windows provide status regarding the RTS and all of the navigation sensors that are present. Data logging provides fix histories for GPS and OMEGA, as well as a history of the ships movement and navigator choices for the past 8 hours. There are several single key operations available to the operator, for example: return to base display, man overboard emergency.

ECDIS COMPLIANCE

The International Hydrographic Organization (IHO) and the International Maritime Organization (IMO) have formed a committee called the Harmonization Group on ECDIS, called HGE. The HGE has been operating for about three years to resolve the differences in ECDIS performance standards generated by both organizations. The current version is called the "Draft Performance Standard for Electronic Chart Display and Information System (ECDIS)", dated 28 April 93.

The Department of Defense (through the DMA and to a lesser degree the Navy) and the Department of Transportation (through the Coast Guard) have been active participants in the HGE process. The ECDIS Performance Standard basically outlines the minimum capabilities a system must meet to be called an ECDIS and to be accepted as a legal means of navigation, ie. replacing use of the paper chart in the bridge (also Combat Information Center (CIC) in Navy vessels). The standard provides minimum levels of performance for the hardware, software and operational procedures without regard to a certain manufacturer. The primary function of the ECDIS is to contribute to safe navigation.

The NAVSSI system has been designed to adhere to the ECDIS Performance Standard, and in most instances exceeds the minimum requirements. The NAVSSI has additional burdens levied upon the system (prime example: additional I/O requirements) that a commercial ECDIS system would not have. Despite this burden, NAVSSI will meet or exceed the performance standards. The performance standard is a draft version and there are some issues to be resolved. Many parties have expressed concern over the ability of a system using the DNC database to meet ECDIS performance standards, citing a potential conflict with the DX-90 data source capability for ECDIS. However, a report by the Intergraph

Corporation (prepared for Woods Hole Oceanographic Institute and the Coast Guard) examines this questions and concludes "nothing seems to threaten the DNC ability to meet ECDIS specifications". As the ECDIS performance standard evolves the NAVSSI system can also evolve to remain in compliance.

CURRENT TECHNICAL STATUS

As of the date of preparation of this paper, January 1994, the NAVSSI Block 1 System was preparing to go through a testing cycle. The Block 1 system consists of upgrades to both the hardware and software of Block 0. Block 0 systems have been installed and currently operate in USS Arkansas and USS John Young.

This upcoming testing cycle consists of essentially four phases. Phase 1 would be internal laboratory testing at NUWC in Norfolk, VA. Phase 2 is Land Based Testing at the NSWC, Dahlgren, VA. Phase 3 is the conduct of TECHEVAL (DT), currently planned to occur in the USS Peterson. The final testing, Phase 4, is OPEVAL (OT). OPEVAL is conducted by OPTEVFOR, Norfolk, VA. This is independent testing to assess operational effectiveness and suitability.

CONCLUSION

The U.S. Navy stands poised to test and evaluate and ECDIS system that operates with the DNC database. Results of this testing will be incorporated into the NAVSSI system operational capabilities and the Navy will then have a compliant ECDIS system. One of the many functions of NAVSSI, and the primary function of an ECDIS, is to contribute to safe navigation. The goal is for the Navy to be using an ECDIS (NAVSSI) to navigate with by the year 2000.

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